

NOTES

The more negative ΔG° values at the higher temperature show that the transfer of aniline from water to the organic layer occurs more readily at elevated temperatures.

The positive values of ΔS° indicate that the transfer of aniline from water layer to the organic layer results in a greater randomness in orientation of aniline molecules with the organic solvent molecules. This is obviously due to the highly polar nature of water molecules resulting in a greater order in the intermolecular orientation of polar aniline with them than with non-polar carbon tetrachloride and benzene molecules. Since nitrobenzene is the most polar among the three liquids studied, the ΔS° value is the least with it.

Even though carbon tetrachloride and benzene are both classified as non-polar, the C-Cl bond in the former is more polarisable than the C-H bond in the latter. Hence the possibility of a greater order in the intermolecular orientation of aniline with carbon tetrachloride than with benzene cannot be ruled out. This is confirmed by the greater ΔS° value with benzene (7.27 e.u.) than with carbon tetrachloride (6.20 e.u.).

The $\Delta \Delta S^\circ$ values obtained with mixtures of the two pairs of the organic solvents (Table 1 and Table 2) show that the carbon tetrachloride-nitrobenzene system exhibits a positive deviation from ideal behaviour (i.e. from the simple mixture rule) while with the carbon-tetrachloride-benzene system the deviation is negative. Further the deviation, positive or negative, appears to be maximum at about 50% composition. This might be due to the greater orderly intermolecular orientation among molecules of carbon tetrachloride and nitrobenzene than among molecules of carbon tetrachloride and benzene. Under such circumstances when aniline molecules get transferred from water to the carbon tetrachloride-nitrobenzene mixture a slightly more randomness of orientation results than there would be if the systems were ideal.

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Condensation of *o*-Phenylenediamine with Ethyl Acetoacetate in presence of Polyphosphoric acid.

(Mrs) K. C. DESAI and C. M. DFSAI

P. T. Sarvajani College of Science, Surat

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ETHYL acetoacetate gives with the diamine under acid condition ethyl β -2-amino-anilinoacronate (m.p. 59°) which undergoes isomerisation to the stable form after eight days (m. p. 85°) in the presence of light; ^{1,2,3} in the present work such a *cis-trans* interconversion could be brought about by treatment with boiling water. Sexton¹ obtained in such a condensation a seven-membered ring compound(I) in neutral boiling Xylene; benzimidazole-2-acetone(II) in alkaline condition and 2-methyl-benzimidazole(III) by heating the crotonate alone at 100°.

He concluded that (I) or (II) might have been formed from the intermediate, acetoacet-*o*-aminoanilide(IV) which he, however, could not isolate.

In the present work such a condensation gave with polyphosphoric acid the above four products but each under different experimental condition. It was however observed in numerous experiments that benzimidazole-2-acetone was obtained at temperatures 120-140° as a stable product and acetoacet-*o*-aminoanilide at 100° under controlled condition; its benzene solution on boiling gave benzimidazole-2-acetone. The variation in the nature of products obtained may be explained on the basis of the exceptional nature of the reagent⁴ and the functional multiplicity of the β -keto ester and diamine.

Experimental

Seven-Membered Ring Compound (I): Freshly prepared polyphosphoric acid (12. ml; 20 g.) was slowly added to an externally ice-cooled mixture of the diamine (5.4g.) and the keto ester (6.8 ml). The reaction mass was heated to 85° and then kept for 24 hours. It was then heated to 150°, treated with ice and neutralised giving a product which was crystallised from alcohol (m.p. 120° - 121°). Its mixed m.p. with the product obtained by the method of Sexton did not show any depression.

Benzimidazole-2-acetone (II): The mixture of the diamine(5.4g.) with the β -ketoester(7 ml.) was mixed with freshly prepared warm PPA (12ml; 20g.), when a vigorous reaction set in with effervescence. It was heated to 150° and kept at this temperature for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. Neutralisation in presence of ice with sodium and ammonium hydroxide solutions precipitated a product. Needles from water (2.2g, m.p. 148°), lit.¹ m.p. 148°.

2-Methyl-benzimidazole (III): Hot PPA (12ml; 20g) was added to a reaction mass of the diamine (5.4g) and the β -ketoester (7.0ml) containing a drop of concentrated hydrochloric acid. Turbid layer, separated during reaction, disappeared on stirring. The reaction mass was stirred at 120-130° for 2½ hours. It was treated with ice and just neutralised; the product (3.2g.) was crystallised from hot water; m. p. 175°; its mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen of 2-methyl-benzimidazole was undepressed.

Acetoacet-o-aminoanilide (IV): *o*-Phenylenediamine (5.4g) was added to a solution of orthophosphoric acid (12 ml) containing β -ketoester (6.8 ml), externally cooled with ice; phosphorous pentoxide (20g) was added to this solution in small lots; the mixture was then heated on steam-bath for ½ hour. The reaction mass was treated with ice and neutralised with ammonium and sodium hydroxide giving yellow product. Yellow needles from aqueous ethanol (2.68g; m.p. 105° dec).

Analysis: $C_{10}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 14.58%
 found N, 14.50%

It coupled with diazotised amines giving deep red colour; its benzene solution on boiling gave benzimidazole-2-acetone (m.p. 118°).

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Acid Catalysed Isomerisation of 3-Epi-Moretenyl Acetate

H N. KHASTGIR* and B. P. PRADHAN

Department of Chemistry, University of North Bengal, Dt. Darjeeling

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3-EPI-MORETENYL acetate¹ (I) on acid isomerisation under mild condition of Fazakerley and co-workers² ($AcOH-H_2SO_4$) furnished hop-17(21)-en-3 α -yl acetate (II), m. p. 222-23°, $[\alpha]_D + 11.1^\circ$. The acetate (II) on

hydrolysis (Methanolic-KOH) gave the corresponding alcohol-hop-17(21)-en-3 α -ol^{3,4} (III), m. p. 185-86°, $[\alpha]_D + 47^\circ$ which on oxidation with CrO_3 -Py complex yielded hopenone-I (identified by m. m. p and IR comparison with an authentic sample prepared from moretenone¹). The alcohol (III) was also prepared from hopenone-I by Meerwein-Pondorff reduction⁵ and was found to be identical (m. m. p. and IR).

Hop-17(21)-en-3 α -yl acetate on further isomerisation under strong acid condition of Fazakerley and co-workers² ($AcOH-C_6H_5-H_2SO_4$) yielded an acetate, hop-13(18)-en-3 α -yl acetate, (IV), m. p. 179-81°, $[\alpha]_D - 32.1^\circ$, which on hydrolysis (Methanolic-KOH) furnished the alcohol, hop-13(18)-en-3 α -ol, (V), m. p. 219-21°, $[\alpha]_D - 14.8^\circ$. Oxidation (CrO_3 -Py) of the alcohol (V) furnished a ketone, m. p. 148-50°, $[\alpha]_D 49^\circ$, identical with hopenone-II (m. m. p). Meerwein-Pondorff reduction⁵ of Hopenone-II yielded an alcohol which was found to be identical with the alcohol (V) and its acetate with (IV) (m.m.p)

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